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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE INTERNATIONAL REGIME FOR THE PROTECTION OF STATELESS PERSONS AND THE RECOGNITION OF THEIR LEGAL STATUS IN BRAZILIAN LEGISLATION.

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Policy Statement

This policy brief analyzes the institution of nationality and its status as a human right to understand how a State exercises its sovereign right to define its nationals. Thus, the duty imposed on States to avoid statelessness is investigated, noting that the improvement of national legislation, as well as access to institutions responsible for analyzing statelessness situations, are fundamental to the eradication of political marginalization and social protection of stateless persons per the provisions of Sustainable Development Goal No. 10. From this perspective, the recognition of the status of stateless persons in the Brazilian Migration Law is analyzed based on the international Conventions that form part of the protection regime for stateless persons.

Background

The situation of statelessness is inextricably linked to the right to nationality. From an institutional standpoint, nationality is generally defined as the political and legal bond that links a person to a State, from which a series of reciprocal rights and duties arise. This bond has, on the one hand, a normative-legal dimension, given that the institution of nationality is regulated by rules established in the legal system of each State. On the other hand, the bond of nationality has a political dimension involving the exercise of state power to discretionarily define the rules and requirements for an individual's acquisition and loss of nationality (Husek, 2022). In other words, stemming from the exercise of state sovereignty, nationality issues fall under each State's internal jurisdiction, which can regulate them through the Constitution, a presidential decree, or a nationality law.

Within the scope of the International Standards Regime of the Right to Nationality, the concept that nationality is a manifestation of a States' sovereignty is reinforced in the following international instruments (IPU, 2009):

- The Permanent Court of International Justice: Advisory Opinion on the Tunis and Morocco Nationality Decrees, 1923.

- The 1930 Hague Convention on Certain Questions Relating to the Conflict of Nationality Laws: "It is for each State to determine who its nationals are under its law. Other States shall recognize this law as it is consistent with international conventions, international custom, and the principles of law generally recognized concerning nationality".
- The International Court of Justice, in the *Nottebohm Case* in 1955: "According to the practice of States, to arbitral and judicial decisions and the opinion of writers, nationality is a legal bond having as its basis a social fact of attachment, a genuine connection of existence, interest, and sentiments, together with the existence of reciprocal rights and duties."
- European Convention on Nationality, 1997.
- The Inter-American Court of Human Rights: *Castillo-Petruzzi et al. v. Peru*, Judgment of May 1999, IACHR (ser.C) No. 52 1999: "the political and legal bond that links a person to a given State and binds him to it with ties of loyalty and fidelity, entitling him to diplomatic protection from that State."

Nationality can be conferred by operation of law based on a principle of *jus soli*, whereby an individual is considered a national of a State in which was born. Alternatively, it can be conferred based on a principle of *jus sanguinis*, whereby a State grants an individual the nationality of their parents, regardless of their place of birth. Additionally, States may adopt the naturalization process to grant their nationality, provided such naturalization is voluntarily requested.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948) and the American Convention on Human Rights (OAS, 1969) enshrine the right to nationality as a fundamental human right. In addition to affirming that every person has the right to a nationality, they also establish that no one should be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality or the right to change it. Consequently, how a State exercises its sovereign right to define its nationals must adhere to international human rights standards, imposing on States the obligation to prevent the creation of statelessness.

According to the Convention Relating to the Status of Stateless Persons (UN, 1954), the term "stateless person" designates any person not considered a national by any State. These are the so-called *de jure* stateless persons, that is, people who did not receive nationality from a State because they did not comply with the requirements for acquiring nationality under current State legislation. On the other hand, a person who

has a formal link of nationality but cannot enjoy the protection of that State like other nationals can be defined as de facto stateless. However, as they are not included in the definition provided for in the 1954 Convention, they are not afforded the protection provided for de jure stateless persons (UNHCR, 2014a).

Considering that it is through nationality that a person receives the protection of a State, stateless people find themselves in a situation of extreme vulnerability and social and political marginalization. This is because, without nationality, even the most basic rights, such as the right to education, medical care, and employment, are denied to individuals who cannot prove the link of nationality with a country. Furthermore, "Without citizenship, a person cannot register to vote in the country in which they are living, cannot apply for a travel document, cannot register to marry. In some instances, individuals who are stateless and are outside their country of origin or country of former residence can be detained for long periods if those countries refuse to grant them re-entry to their territories" (IPU, 2009).

There are several reasons why a person becomes stateless. According to the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR, 2014b), statelessness can occur due to discrimination against particular ethnic or religious groups or based on gender, migration or displacement, the emergence of new States and transfers of territories between existing States, and gaps in nationality laws. Regardless of the reason for statelessness, it is closely linked to the internal jurisdiction of each State in defining the requirements and procedures for determining nationality.

At the international level, the obligation imposed on States to avoid statelessness arises directly from the principle of equality and non-discrimination, which is part of General International Law and is considered an integral part of jus cogens, that is, the set of peremptory norms of general international law that must be observed and cannot be violated, as provided for in Article 53 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (UN, 1969), and enshrined by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights in the Case of Veliz Franco et al. v. Guatemala in Judgment of May 19, 2014.

In this context, considering that States are responsible for implementing the legal reforms necessary to address the phenomenon of statelessness, we will examine the case of Brazil by analyzing how it legally positions itself in the challenge of realizing the human rights of stateless persons within its constitutional and international commitment to eradicating marginalization and reducing social inequalities.

Findings

According to the UN Refugee Agency (2020), millions worldwide do not have a nationality. In 2020, an estimated 4.2 million people lived in a situation of statelessness. However, the current number of stateless people could be substantially higher. In 2015, the UN estimated that around 10 million children are stateless.

At a regional level, the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (2003), in the Advisory Opinion on the Juridical Condition and Rights of Undocumented Migrants, delivered on September 17, 2003, determined that "the State, both internationally and in its domestic legal system, and through the acts of any of its powers or of third parties who act under its tolerance, acquiescence or negligence, cannot behave in a way that is contrary to the principle of equality and non-discrimination, to the detriment of a determined group of persons."

Therefore, given that stateless persons are guaranteed equal and non-discriminatory treatment under the domestic order of a State, one of the primary challenges these individuals face is the process of recognizing their legal status. This is because, despite the 1954 Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons defining the term "stateless," there is no provision outlining the procedure for identifying statelessness. Such recognition is fundamental for stateless persons to enjoy the rights provided for in the 1954 Convention. In 1961, the UN Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness stipulated that nationality must be granted at birth or upon an application being lodged with the appropriate State authority, per its national legislation. Thus, States must define the procedures for identifying stateless individuals and determining their legal status.

The 1954 Convention Relating to the Status of Stateless Persons was incorporated into the Brazilian legal system through Decree No. 4,246 of 2002, while the Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness cases was incorporated through Decree No. 8,501 of 2015. These ratifications demonstrate Brazil's commitment to reducing statelessness under international law. In 2017, Migration Law No. 13,445 was enacted to establish the principles and guidelines for public policies related to migration. This law defines a stateless person as "a person who is not considered a national by any State, according to its legislation, under the terms of the Convention on the Status of

Stateless Persons, of 1954, promulgated by Decree No. 4,246, May 22, 2002, or so recognized by the Brazilian State" (Brasil, 2017).

The Brazilian Migration Law regulates the statelessness determination procedure in Article 26. This process aims to verify whether the applicant is considered a national by the legislation of any State. Once Brazil recognizes its status as a stateless person, they are guaranteed access to the rights and protections provided for in the 1954 Convention and other rights and protections recognized by the State in Brazilian territory. Upon recognition of stateless legal status, the legislation also provides that the applicant must be consulted about their desire to acquire Brazilian nationality through naturalization. If they choose to naturalize, the stateless person must demonstrate that they are legally capable, according to Brazilian law, and prove residence in the national territory for a minimum period of two years, in addition to complying with other requirements and duties listed in the Migration Law. The process of naturalizing a stateless person is simplified, being carried out within 30 (thirty) days (Brasil, 2017). A permanent residence permit will be granted if the recognized stateless person does not opt for immediate naturalization. In this way, the stateless person now has a legal personality that guarantees them to enjoy the fundamental rights inherent to the human person.

Through an analysis of the Brazilian Migration Law, it is evident that Brazil's commitment to protecting stateless individuals and preventing statelessness aligns directly with the fundamental objectives of the Federal Republic of Brazil (1988), as outlined in Article 3 of the Constitution, namely, fostering a free, just, and supportive society, eradicating poverty and marginalization, and reducing social inequalities.

Internationally, this commitment is reflected in SDG 10, which aims to reduce inequalities by promoting social, economic, and political inclusion for all, regardless of age, gender, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion, or financial status. According to UNHCR (2021), Brazil has made significant contributions to the issue of statelessness, additionally ensuring "through its legislation, procedures for determining statelessness, as well as facilitated naturalization procedures for people recognized as stateless." Furthermore, the Brazilian mechanisms for determining statelessness enable individuals to enjoy the legal status that allows residence and guaranteed access to public services in Brazilian territory, facilitating regular and responsible migration under target 10.7 of SDG 10.

Recommendations

The non-recognition of a person's legal personality through nationality violates the dignity of the human person, as per the understanding established by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (2005) in the Case of the Girls Yean and Bosico v. Dominican Republic in Judgment of September 8, 2005, in which "The Court considers that the failure to recognize juridical personality harms human dignity because it denies absolutely an individual's condition of being a subject of rights and renders him vulnerable to non-observance of his rights by the State or other individuals."

In this context, it is recommended that national legislation be enhanced, along with improved access to institutions responsible for analyzing the situations of statelessness. This includes eliminating the de facto statelessness, as these measures constitute fundamental mechanisms for eradicating stateless people's political and social marginalization.

Considering that 94 countries are parties to the 1954 Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons and 75 countries have become signatories to the 1961 Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness (UNHCR, n.d.), it is recommended to promote international debate so that more States encourage adherence to the two UN Conventions on Statelessness. Additionally, efforts should be undertaken to establish or improve procedures for recognizing stateless legal status to provide these individuals with access to fundamental rights, following the example set by Brazil.

Conclusions

"One day, I was standing between the borders and could not get into either country. It was the most unforgettable experience in my life! I could not enter the State Where I had been; also I couldn't get into the State Where I was born, raised and lived! Where do I belong? I still cannot forget the strong feeling of loss I experienced at the airport". Chen, who was formerly stateless (IPU, 2009).

"Being said 'No' to by the country where I live; being said 'No' to by the country where I was born; being said 'No' to by the country where my parents are from; hearing 'you do not belong to us' continuously! I feel I am nobody and don't even know why I'm living. Being stateless, you are Always surrounded by a sense of worthlessness".

Lara, who was formerly stateless (IPU, 2009).

"We can't get regular jobs, we can't move, we are like boats without ports. Access to education and health care are also problems. I couldn't finish high school or go to college. I can only see a doctor in a private hospital, not in the government ones".

Abdullah, a stateless

Bidoon living in the United Arab Emirates (IPU, 2009).

The three statements above, extracted from the Handbook prepared for Parliamentarians by the Inter-Parliamentary Union's (IPU, 2009) Committee to Promote Respect for International Humanitarian Law, condemn the erasure of individuals in situations of statelessness, who are rendered invisible and denied their most fundamental rights.

Nationality is a fundamental human right that grants individuals both duties and responsibilities. Holding the nationality of a State not only provides individuals with a sense of identity but also guarantees them the protection of the State of which they are nationals.

However, while the granting of nationality to an individual stems from the exercise of state sovereignty, it is simultaneously the responsibility of States to implement the necessary legal reforms to address the phenomenon of statelessness. In this regard, strengthening national institutions responsible for recognizing statelessness, including through international cooperation, is crucial for implementing policies that reduce inequalities and eradicate social marginalization. In federal legislation establishing the procedure for identifying the legal status of a stateless person, as occurs in Brazil, a State allows stateless people access to essential services, thereby reducing vulnerability and political and social marginalization for these individuals.

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